

PROGRESSIVE FATIGUE MODELING OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PINNED/BOLTED CONNECTIONS

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SUMMARY: In this research, a deterministic model for predicting the behaviour of laminated composite pinned/bolted connections under fatigue loading is described. A phenomenological modeling technique, called *progressive fatigue damage modeling*, is established which is capable of predicting the residual strength, residual stiffness, and fatigue life of composite laminates. Stress analysis, failure analysis, and material property degradation rules are the three major components of the model. A three dimensional, nonlinear, finite element technique is proposed for the stress analysis. Based on the state of stress, different failure modes are detected by a set of fatigue failure criteria. To remove the requirement of the large experimental data base for the failure analysis a normalization technique is established. By using this technique the restriction of the application of the failure criteria to limited states of stresses is overcome. Material properties of each element are degraded by using *sudden* and *gradual* material property degradation rules. For this purpose an analytical technique is established to predict the degradation of material properties of a unidirectional ply under multiaxial fatigue loading. Based on the *model*, a computer code is developed that simulates cycle by cycle behaviour of composite laminates under fatigue loading.

KEYWORDS: fatigue, pin, bolt, progressive modeling, failure criteria

INTRODUCTION

One of the earliest papers in fatigue of composite laminates with stress concentrations was published by Owen and Bishop [1]. Today, there are several experimental [2-5] and analytical [6-8] research papers in this field. However, the present state of knowledge is still in the stage of development and improvement. Among the existing models, the semi-empirical model of Kulkarni *et al.* [6], the critical element model of Reifsnider *et al.* [7], and the damage growth model of Spearing *et al.* [8] are all systematic and methodological, therefore they are worthwhile for discussion. The semi-empirical model of Kulkarni *et al.* [6] was developed based on a mechanistic wearout [9] framework. The wearout philosophy treats fatigue damage as the growth of pre-existing flaws or discontinuities in a material. By growing the flaws, the strength of the material decreases and reaches to the level of the state of stress and finally, catastrophic fatigue failure occurs. The semi-empirical model was evaluated by experimental techniques, but little correlation between the theory and

experiments was found. Although the semi-empirical model of Kulkarni *et al.* [6] never showed a correlation with experimental results, there are however many interesting points and valuable information in their work. The critical element model of Reifsnider *et al.* [7] was developed based on a mechanistic approach. Their mechanistic approach is based on micromechanical representations of strength. Sendekyj [10] listed some of the weaknesses of this model. In the critical model, it is assumed that failure occurs suddenly and everywhere in the lamina, which is not consistent with the experimental observations. Also in the model, the dependence of lamina failure stresses on the lamina thickness in laminates is not properly considered. Moreover, the model does not properly account for delamination between the laminae in the laminate. The damage growth model of Spearing *et al.* [8] is based on quantification of notch tip damage by the extent of the individual failure processes, such as splitting in the 0° plies and delamination between the 0° ply and off-axis plies. There are some limitations in the damage growth model which are listed here. The model is laminate geometry dependent, i.e., by changing the lay-up of the laminate, the model must be modified. Moreover, the existence of transverse ply cracks, which is an important failure mode, is ignored in their model. Furthermore, they assume that the damage pattern is similar in all plies and delamination shape is the same at all interfaces which is not a general assumption. Also, the shape of the notch is pre-defined. In addition, their model is only capable of considering cyclic tensile loading. Thus all existing models for fatigue analysis of composites have limitations which make them unsuitable for general use.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Consider a composite plate with a hole under fatigue pin/bolt loading. The coordinate axes, dimensions, and variables are shown in Fig. 1. At the start of cyclic loading, the strength of the material is greater than the stress state, therefore there is no static mode of failure anywhere on the plate. By increasing the number of cycles from zero, based on the stress states at each point of the plate, material properties at those points are degraded as a function of number of cycles. By increasing number of cycles with more degradation of the material properties and redistribution of stresses, failure begins in regions where the strength of the material is less than the stress state at that point. After failure initiation, stresses are redistributed around failed regions. By further increasing the number of cycles, failure propagates in different directions. Finally after a certain number of cycles the laminate cannot tolerate additional cycles. At this point the maximum number of cycles is reached and the laminate has failed completely.

Fig. 1: Composite plate under pin/bolt load

COMPONENTS OF THE MODEL

Progressive fatigue damage model is an integration of three major components. These are stress analysis, failure analysis, and material property degradation rules. There are some similarities between static and fatigue progressive damage modeling. However, there are many features in fatigue progressive damage modeling that make this technique quite different from static progressive damage modeling. Details of these differences will be more clear in the next sections. In the following, after a brief explanation of each component, the model is established by the integration of the three components.

Stress Analysis

By considering edge effects, delamination, out-of-plane buckling, and stacking sequence effects that are fully three dimensional phenomena, and because of material nonlinearity, a three dimensional nonlinear finite element technique is used for the stress analysis. Assuming symmetric geometry, loading, and ply lay-up, suitable boundary conditions are used (Fig. 2). Radial fixed displacement boundary conditions have been applied on nodes around the hole at the load region to simulate the pin load. To simulate a fully tightened bolt, a uniform pressure is applied on the washer region. Moreover, to simulate friction between the washer and the plate, fixed displacement boundary conditions in radial and tangential directions are applied on nodes on the surface of the composite plate and under the washer region. The material properties of a unidirectional ply are assumed to be transversely isotropic. By this assumption, in three dimensions, the number of material parameters (strengths, stiffnesses, and Poisson's ratios) is reduced from eighteen to eleven. To achieve high accuracy, the isoparametric quadratic 20-node brick element was used. Also by using a large number of elements near the edge of the hole and at layer interfaces, stress singularities have been considered.

Fig. 2: Finite element model

Failure Analysis

Despite the existence of an extensive amount of research on biaxial/multi-axial fatigue of metals [11], research in the same field on composite materials [12,13] is less complete. Literature reviews on multi-axial and biaxial fatigue loading of composite materials presented by Found [12], and Chen and Matthews [13] state that further research in this field is needed.

In this research, seven different failure modes for the unidirectional ply under multi-axial state of stress are considered which are: fiber tension, fiber compression, fiber-matrix shearing, matrix tension, matrix compression, normal tension and normal compression failure modes. Suitable stress-based failure criteria for detecting these modes of failure under static and fatigue loading conditions are derived. The effect of material nonlinearity on the mathematical form of the failure criteria is also considered. Difficulties and limitations of application of such failure criteria, in traditional forms, for unidirectional plies under multi-axial fatigue loading conditions for general stress state and stress ratios are discussed. Under fatigue loading conditions, the material is loaded by a stress state which is less than the maximum strength of the material, therefore there is no static mode of failure. However, by increasing the number of cycles, the material properties degrade and eventually lower to the level of the stress state and, at this point, catastrophic failure occurs. The idea of using polynomial failure criteria to predict the life of a composite ply under multi-axial fatigue loading has been utilized by many investigators [14-16]. They used the fatigue strength, as a function of number of cycles, in the denominators of failure criteria instead of the static strength of the material. This strategy is potentially beneficial, however in practice, the application of their models are restricted to very specific conditions.

To show the restriction of application of fatigue failure criteria in traditional forms, consider the following fatigue failure criterion introduced by Hashin [15] for fiber tension fatigue failure mode of a unidirectional ply under a two-dimensional state of stress (biaxial fatigue),

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{xx}}{X_t(n, \sigma, \kappa)} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{xy}}{S_{xy}(n, \sigma, \kappa)} \right)^2 = g_{f+}^2 \quad (\text{if } g_{f+} > 1, \text{ then failure}) \quad (1)$$

where $X_t(n, \sigma, \kappa)$ is the residual longitudinal tensile strength of a unidirectional ply under uniaxial fatigue loading, and $S_{xy}(n, \sigma, \kappa)$ is the residual in-plane shear strength of a unidirectional ply under uniaxial shear fatigue loading conditions. Both X_t and S_{xy} are functions of n , σ and κ , which are number of cycles, stress state and stress ratio, respectively. In practice, designers must deal with a wide range of states of stress, varying from low to high. Therefore, in order to apply Eq. 1, the residual longitudinal tensile fatigue strength and

residual in-plane shear fatigue strength of a unidirectional ply ($X_{i,(n,\sigma,\kappa)}$ and $S_{xy,(n,\sigma,\kappa)}$) must be fully characterized under different stress levels and stress ratios. This requires a large quantity of experiments just to predict the fiber in tension fatigue failure mode of a unidirectional ply under simple biaxial fatigue loading conditions. By considering the other modes of failure and the multiaxial states of stress which are encountered in the real fatigue design of composite structures, the proposed method is faced with severe difficulties.

To overcome the difficulties arising from the large quantity of experiments required at different stress states and stress ratios to characterize the material, many investigators [14-16] restricted their models to specific stress ratios. This assumption is too restrictive for general cases. For example, in the analysis of a pin/bolt fatigue loaded composite laminate, using a constant stress ratio leads to incorrect results. Clearly, for this problem there are different states of stress at different points in the material. Also, after applying fatigue load on a notched composite laminate, failure initiates near the stress concentrations and the material property degrades, therefore the stress ratio and the state of stress are not constant at different points. This means that in practice, stresses redistribute during the fatigue loading. By considering the different behaviour of a unidirectional ply for each combination of the stress state and stress ratio, an infinite number of experiments would be required in order to fully characterize the residual properties of a unidirectional ply under arbitrary state of stress and stress ratio. To eliminate the aforementioned obstacle of using the quadratic polynomial failure criteria for a wide range of stress state and stress ratio, a novel technique (generalized residual material property degradation model) which has been explained in detail in other articles [17,18] published by authors. The fatigue failure criteria for different modes of failure are similar to static failure criteria, except that the material properties are not constants but functions of number of cycles, stress state, and stress ratios. It should be added that the effects of material nonlinearity on the fatigue failure criteria are also considered. A list of different fatigue failure criteria suitable for detecting various modes of failure is explained elsewhere [19] and for brevity is not repeated in this paper.

Material Property Degradation

As failure occurs in a ply of a laminate, material properties of that failed ply are changed by the material property degradation rules. For each mode of failure, there exists an appropriate *sudden* material property degradation rule. Some of the failure criteria are catastrophic and some of them are not. Thus for each failure mode a suitable rule exists. For instance, after detecting fiber tension failure mode, which is a catastrophic mode, all of the stiffnesses and Poisson's ratios of the failed ply are reduced abruptly to zero. As another example, for matrix tension failure mode, only the transverse stiffness and Poisson's ratios are changed to zero. Moreover in fatigue loading, after each number of cycles, material properties of each ply (strengths, stiffnesses, and Poisson's ratios) are degraded, even though failure is not detected by any of the above mentioned failure criteria. For this purpose an analytical technique is established to predict the *gradual* degradation of material properties of a unidirectional ply under multiaxial fatigue loading.

The residual strength of a unidirectional ply under arbitrary uniaxial state of stress and stress ratio is calculated using the following equation:

$$R(n, \sigma, \kappa) = \left[1 - \left(\frac{\log(n) - \log(.25)}{\log(N_f) - \log(.25)} \right)^\beta \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} (R_s - \sigma) + \sigma \quad (2)$$

where, $R(n, \sigma, \kappa)$ = residual strength, R_s = static strength, n = number of applied cycles, σ = magnitude of applied maximum stress, N_f = fatigue life at σ , κ = stress ratio, and α and β = experimental curve fitting parameters. The residual stiffness of a unidirectional ply under arbitrary uniaxial state of stress and stress ratio is calculated using the following equation:

$$E(n, \sigma, \kappa) = \left[1 - \left(\frac{\log(n) - \log(.25)}{\log(N_f) - \log(.25)} \right)^\lambda \right]^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \left(E_s - \frac{\sigma}{\epsilon_f} \right) + \frac{\sigma}{\epsilon_f} \quad (3)$$

where, $E(n, \sigma, \kappa)$ = residual stiffness, E_s = static stiffness, ϵ_f = average strain to failure, and γ and λ = experimental curve fitting parameters. The normalized fatigue life of a unidirectional ply under arbitrary uniaxial state of stress and stress ratio is calculated using the following equation:

$$u = \frac{\ln(a/f)}{\ln[(1-q)(c+q)]} = A + B \log N_f \quad (4)$$

where, f and u = curve fitting parameters, $\sigma_a = (\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min})/2$ = alternating stress, $\sigma_m = (\sigma_{\max} + \sigma_{\min})/2$ = mean stress, $q = \sigma_m/\sigma_t$, $a = \sigma_a/\sigma_t$, $c = \sigma_c/\sigma_t$, σ_t = tensile strength, σ_c = compressive strength. For the shear loading condition Eq. 4 must be modified. For a unidirectional ply under shear, the definitions of tensile strength and compression strength are meaningless, i.e., there is no difference between positive and negative shear. Therefore, the word strength is used instead. By considering this, the parameter “c” in Eq. 4 is equal to one ($c=1$) for shear fatigue conditions. Also, the experimental results for unidirectional plies under in-plane shear loading conditions show that a better curve fitting is achieved by adding a “ \log_{10} ” to the left-hand side of Eq. 4. Therefore, Eq. 4 is changed to the following form for the simulation of fatigue life of the unidirectional ply under shear loading conditions. The left-hand side of Eq. 5 is still denoted by “u” for brevity.

$$u = \log_{10} \left(\frac{\ln(a/f)}{\ln[(1-q)(1+q)]} \right) = A + B \log N_f \quad (5)$$

PROGRESSIVE FATIGUE DAMAGE MODEL

The model is explained by means of a flowchart shown in Fig. 3. As shown in this figure, the finite element model must first be prepared. In this step, material properties, geometry, boundary conditions, maximum and minimum fatigue load, maximum number of cycles, incremental number of cycles, etc., are defined. Then the stress analysis, based on the maximum and minimum fatigue load, is performed. Consequently, the maximum and minimum induced on-axis stresses of all elements are calculated. It should be emphasized that on-axis stresses for each ply of each laminate of each element at Gauss points are

calculated and averaged. Therefore, the stress ratio ($\kappa = \sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}$) for each element is determined. In the next step, failure analysis is performed and the maximum stresses are examined by the set of fatigue failure criteria. If there is a sudden mode of failure, then the material properties of the failed plies are changed according to appropriate *sudden* material property degradation rules. The stiffness matrix of the finite element model is rebuilt and the stress analysis is performed again. New stresses are examined by the set of fatigue failure criteria. In this step, if there is no sudden mode of failure, an incremental number of cycles are applied (e.g., $\delta n = 100$). If the number of cycles is greater than a preset total number of cycles, then the computer program stops. Otherwise, material properties of all plies of all elements are changed according to *gradual* material property degradation rules using the *generalized material property degradation technique*. Then stress analysis is performed again and the above loop is repeated until catastrophic failure occurs, or the maximum number of cycles (pre-defined by the user) is reached. If catastrophic failure is reached, then fatigue life and the mechanisms of failure due to fatigue loading have been achieved. It should be noted that if the maximum number of cycles is selected as a large number, such as 10^9 , then the fatigue life of the problem can be obtained by the algorithm. If the computer program stops because the user-chosen maximum number of cycles is reached, then the mechanisms of failure due to fatigue loading are found by examining the final state of damage. Furthermore, in the latter case, residual strength of the composite laminate is obtainable by performing a progressive static damage modeling on the final results of *progressive fatigue damage model*.

Fig. 3: Flowchart of progressive fatigue damage model

In order to verify the *fatigue progressive damage model*, a complete knowledge of material properties (stiffness, strength, and fatigue life) of a unidirectional ply under static and fatigue loading conditions is required. Hence, to run the computer program developed for *progressive fatigue modeling* of laminated composites, the mechanical behaviour of a unidirectional ply under uniaxial static and fatigue loading conditions must be fully characterized. For this purpose, the material properties of a unidirectional composite laminate in static and fatigue loading conditions; in the fiber and matrix directions; under tensile, compressive, in-plane-shear and out-of-plane-shear loading are required.

RESULTS

To verify the fatigue simulation capability of the *model*, fatigue life and residual strength tests are performed for different ply configurations and load levels. To show the generality of the *model*, simulated results for fatigue life of the pin/bolt-loaded composite laminates are also compared with independent experimental results available in the literature. Also, the residual fatigue life of the pin-loaded composite laminates under two consecutive load levels (low and high) is measured experimentally and the results are compared with simulated results by the *model*. In the following some of the typical results obtained are presented. Additional results are published by the authors elsewhere [17-19]. The results of the fatigue life of pin-loaded $[0_4/90_4]_s$ and $[90_4/0_4]_s$ cross-ply laminates made of AS4/3501-6, are shown in Fig. 4. As shown, similar to the static strength behaviour, the pin-loaded $[90_4/0_4]_s$ laminate shows a higher fatigue life than the $[0_4/90_4]_s$ cross-ply laminate for the same fatigue loading conditions. The main reason for this behaviour is explained by the lower singular stress state for the $[90_4/0_4]_s$ cross-ply laminate near the edge of the hole.

To evaluate the *progressive fatigue damage model* by independent experimental data, the fatigue life of a pin-loaded quasi-isotropic $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ laminate made of AS4/3501-6 is simulated and compared with the experimental results of Herrington and Sabbaghian [20]. The fatigue life of the pin-loaded quasi-isotropic laminate is simulated by the *progressive fatigue damage model* and compared with the experimental results (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4: Fatigue life curves of pin-loaded $[0_4/90_4]_s$ and $[90_4/0_4]_s$ laminates

Fig. 5: Fatigue life of pin-loaded quasi-isotropic $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminates (simulation by the model and experiments by Herrington and Sabbaghian [20])

The progression of damage in a pin-loaded angle-ply $[+45_4/-45_4]_s$ laminate at different number of cycles is shown in Fig. 6. The simulated number of cycles to failure is 25000 cycles, while the experiments show a range of 15000 to 26900 cycles. As shown, an excellent agreement between the simulated and experimental results is achieved for mode of failure.

simulated by the model after 0, 18000 and 25000 fatigue loading cycles

experiment at final failure

Fig. 6: Progression of damage in a pin-loaded angle-ply $[+45_4/-45_4]_s$ laminate

SUMMARY

The present research establishes a new modeling approach to simulate the behaviour of composite laminates under general fatigue loading conditions. Using the idea of the traditional progressive damage model which is capable of simulating of static behaviour of composite laminates, the *progressive fatigue damage model* is developed. The *model* consists of three major components: stress analysis, failure analysis and material property degradation rules. The *model* determines the state of damage at any load level and number of cycles, from failure initiation and propagation to catastrophic failure. The *model* is able to predict the residual strength, residual life, final failure mechanisms and final fatigue life of composite laminates under general fatigue loading conditions. Based on the *model*, a computer code is developed which simulates the cycle-by-cycle behaviour of composite laminates under fatigue loading conditions. The capabilities of the model are examined by simulation of a pin/bolt-loaded composite laminates as a complicated example.

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